

Popular Article

Goat: Foster mother of man & Poor man's cow

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Introduction

At the national level, goats play a significant part in the rural economy. They are raised by more than 70% of landless agricultural laborer's and marginal and small farmers in rural India. For poor farmers, goat farming offers a huge socio-economic benefit when compared to other livestock species. Low input, high fecundity, easy marketing, and unprejudiced social acceptance of their products are just a few of the many benefits of this business that guarantees a greater revenue. Goats are also one of the most common meat producing animals in India, and their flesh (chevon) is widely consumed regardless of caste, creed, or religion. They generate a wide range of items, including meat, milk, skin, fibre, and dung. In 2019, the country's total goat population was 148.88 million, a rise of 10.14% over the previous Livestock Census (2012). Goats account for around 27.8% of total livestock.

Goat milk

1. Goats are known as man's foster mother since their milk is regarded to be superior for human nourishment than that of other animal species.
2. Goat milk is inexpensive, healthy, easy to digest, and nourishing.
3. Goat milk is finer than cow milk, which means the lipids and proteins are present in a finer state and are easier to digest, especially for children and the elderly.
4. Goat milk causes fewer allergy reactions than milk from other animals.
5. Humans have less lactose sensitivity while drinking goat milk
6. Ayurvedic medicine uses goat milk to treat asthma, cough, diabetes, and other ailments.
7. Goat milk has higher buffering qualities and good for patients suffering from peptic ulcers, liver dysfunction, jaundice, biliary disorders and other digestive problems.
8. Goat milk is beneficial for vegetarian communities due to higher phosphate content.
9. Goat milk is known to help in recovery from Dengue fever.
10. Goat milk has a higher content of B-complex vitamins.
11. Goat milk is suitable for preparing various milk products.
12. Goats can be milked as often as required, preventing milk storage problems and refrigeration costs.

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Poor man's cow: Goat has been referred to as a poor man's cow (or mini-cow) due to its significant contribution to the poor man's economy. They not only provide their children with nutritious and easily digestible milk, but also provide a consistent source of supplemental revenue for impoverished and landless or marginal farmers. Women and children may readily manage goats because they are little animals. Feeding, milking, and caring for goats do not necessitate a lot of equipment or effort. Feeding costs and capital investment are both low. Four goats can be kept for the same price as one indigenous cow. Goats can be effectively raised in regions where there are few fodder resources and milch animals do not thrive. Returns on capital of up to 50% and a 70% recovery rate are possible.

Advantages of goat farming / Utility of goats: -

1. Goats provide a variety of products, including meat, milk, hide, fibre, and faeces. In mountainous locations, it's used for light-weight transportation.
2. Goats require little in the way of housing and management. They don't require separate housing and get along swimmingly with their owners' other pets.
3. Goats can be grown by landless agricultural labourers, women, and children since they can eat a variety of leaves, shrubs, bushes, and kitchen waste.
4. Goat farming can be a profitable enterprise for a farmer if it's integrated into a mixed farming operation (mixed farming means animal husbandry and agriculture).
5. Goats are less expensive to keep, have a kind demeanour, and are commonly available.
6. Goats can adapt to a variety of agroclimatic situations, from desert to cold arid to hot and humid. Plains, hilly areas, sandy zones, and high altitudes are all good places to raise them.
7. Goats, on the other hand, are more tolerant of hot weather than other farm animals.
8. Goats have improved crude fibre digestibility and can produce even on low-quality roughages.
9. Goats produce more per unit of investment than other animals.
10. Goats are smaller and slaughtered at an earlier age.
11. There are no religious restrictions on goat meat, and it is consumed by people from all walks of life
12. Goat meat is lower in fat and more popular.
13. The skin of a goat is utilized to make leather products.
14. The hairs of goats are used to make rugs and ropes.
15. Pashmina shawls and Mohair carpets are in high demand and sell for a lot of money.
16. The nitrogen and phosphoric acid content of goat dung is 2.5 times that of cow manure.
17. Goats are a great animal to study for physiological and medicinal studies.

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